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An Investigation of the Relationship Between Preschool Teachers' Individual and Administrative Creativity and Job Satisfaction

Yıldız Güven¹, Dicle Akay², Sümeyye Öcal³

¹ Maltepe University, İstanbul, Türkiye. Email: yildizguven@maltepe.edu.tr

² Bahcesehir University, İstanbul, Türkiye. Email: dicleakay91@gmail.com

³ Istanbul Gelisim University, İstanbul, Türkiye. Email: social@gelisim.edu.tr

Correspondence: Sümeyye Öcal, Vocational College of Health Services, Istanbul Gelisim University, Istanbul, Avcılar, Turkey. Tel: +90531 384 85 55, E-mail: social@gelisim.edu.tr

Abstract

The creativity skills of individuals have started to gain importance in adapting to today's changing conditions. In this context, teachers need to transfer their individual creativity to the organizational environment. In order to do this, they need to provide personal pleasure and satisfaction from their work. The main aim of this study is to examine the relationship between preschool teachers' individual and administrative creativity and job satisfaction. The study, which is designed as relational survey model, was carried out with 173 preschool teachers. The data obtained from Personal Information Form, Organizational Creativity Scale and Job Satisfaction Scale. As a result of the research, the organizational creativity scores of preschool teachers in the dimension of individual creativity showed a significant difference according to the type of institution, and no difference was found according to the status of wanting to do a different profession, the number of students in the class, professional seniority and weekly working hours. There was a difference in the administrative creativity of teachers according to the type of institution, their willingness to do a different profession and the number of students in the classroom, while professional seniority and weekly working hours make no difference. There was a difference among teachers' job satisfaction scores according to the type of institution, their willingness to do a different profession, and the number of children in the classroom, but not according to professional seniority and weekly working hours. According to the result of the research it can be claimed that as the organizational creativity scores of preschool teachers in individual and administrative dimensions increased, their job satisfaction increased too. It was suggested that conditions improving organizational creativity and job satisfactions of preschool teachers should be given place in schools.

Keywords: Preschool Teachers, Individual Creativity, Administrative Creativity, Job Satisfaction

Introduction

It is a well-known fact that information is rapidly renewed in our century and this renewal has significant effects on situations, relationships and products. In such an age, teachers who made important contributions to the development of societies; as their role as transmitters of knowledge decreases, their role as facilitators is

increasing, providing the tools necessary to build on existing knowledge. In this context, it has become more important for teachers to notice changes, adapt to innovations, and develop strategies to cope with problems. These features are largely related to creativity.

Creativity and Organizational Creativity

According to Mumford, Medeiros and Partlow (2012), creativity is essential for partially solved or never solved problems, and only creative thinkers can keep up with the rapid changes in the world. According to the most widely known definition, creativity is the process of being sensitive to problems, inadequacies, lack of information, missing elements and incompatibilities; identifying difficulties, searching for solutions; making predictions or hypotheses about deficiencies and testing them repeatedly; changing and re-testing these when it is necessary and explaining what comes out (Torrance, 1962).

In the past years, creativity was thought to be an individual act; however, the idea that creativity is an ability for organizations has gained importance in recent years (Akman & Abasli, 2017; Cengiz, Acuner & Baki, 2007, Hunter et al., 2005; Nisula, 2013; Shalley & Gilson, 2004). When creativity skills are adapted to the organization, organizations can foresee future changes and are more successful in making quick decisions and taking actions based on these changes (Balay, 2010; Indriartiningtias, Hartono & Subagyo, 2018). Organizational creativity can generally be defined as the ability of employees, individually or as a group, to bring a new product, service, idea, procedure, or process which is valuable, useful, and practical to the organization (Olszak, Bartus & Lorek, 2018; Parjanen, 2012; Shalley, Gilson & Blumsource, 2000; Taggar, 2002; Woodman, Sawyer & Griffin, 1993).

Individual, administrative, and social creativity are addressed together for organizational creativity (Boyacı & Karacabey, 2016; Hirst, Van Dick & Van Knippenberg, 2009). Therefore, these three elements must be related to each other. Individual creativity emerges in problem solving environments in the work and/or daily life and has a positive effect on organizational creativity (Iraz & Akyazi, 2015), administrative creativity is mostly based on the leader's behavior or leadership style in an organization. The level of organizational creativity is an administrative process where managers are responsible for guiding organizations to meet their objectives which require creative problem-solving. On the other hand, another fundamental condition for organizational creativity is the existence of a social environment that allows for creativity (Kwaśniewska & Nęcka, 2004).

Supporting factors for organizational creativity showed that the support of administration, transparency of processes for all employees, financial appreciation of employees such as monetary issues, appreciation of the moral aspects such as approving, empowerment of employees to make decisions and to initiate certain tasks and providing flexibility of risks and uncertainty influence organizational creativity positively (Cengiz et al., 2007). In order to ensure creativity in organizations, it is necessary to identify employees with high intrinsic motivation. The intrinsic motivation mentioned here refers to the personal pleasure and satisfaction of a person is doing and accomplishing a job (Greenberg, 2002). Since schools are an organization, it is natural that subjects that support creativity in organizations also apply to schools.

Job Satisfaction and Organizational Creativity

Job satisfaction can be described as an individual's involvement in an emotional reaction to work environment (Perie & Baker, 1997) and it can be addressed both positively and negatively. From a positive perspective, job satisfaction for an individual is explained as the pleasure that s/he gets from her/his profession or work experiences and their positive emotional consequences for the individual (Duxburg, Armstrong, Drew & Henly, 1984; Izgar, 2000). It is seen that job satisfaction is actually an important factor for the performance and success of all organizations (Dee, 2006). Individual factors affecting job satisfaction can be considered as expectations from the work environment, age, gender, socio-cultural environment, personality, education level, the number of working year, appreciation of the profession, professional seniority (Kılıç, Tanrikulu & Uğur, 2013; Özyürek, 2009; Yılmaz & Izgar, 2009). Environmental factors affecting job satisfaction can be named as the quality of work, wage, working conditions, group interaction, administrator characteristics (Smith, Kendall & Hulin, 1969,

cited in Özkalp, 2013, p. 74). When the factors affecting job satisfaction are considered, it is noticed that these factors also influence organizational creativity.

Studies revealed that an organizational climate that supports the creativity of the employees has a positive effect on their job satisfaction (Abu-Saad & Hendrix, 1995; Baltaş & Baltaş, 2000; Çekmecelioğlu, 2005; Friedman, 1991; Goldberger & Breznitz, 1982; Schwab, Jackson & Schuler, 1986). Job satisfaction is rather seen as a function of the relationship between what teachers want from teaching and what they perceive (Papanastasiou & Zembylas, 2005). Özdemir, Sezgin, Kaya and Receptoğlu (2011) also mention that teaching profession is a strenuous and stressful profession. Also, it is notified that when job satisfaction decreases, job productivity also decreases in many work areas (Keser, 2006). From this point of view, it is inevitable that the quality of education given to students will decrease if job satisfaction of preschool teachers decreases.

When the literature is examined, it is seen that the relational studies on the organizational creativity and job satisfaction levels of preschool teachers do not take place enough in the field. As preschool children will be more affected by the attitudes of the teachers than the children in the older age group because of their closer relationship with teachers, it is possible for preschool teachers to reflect the negative effects of their dissatisfaction to their work environment. Teachers' job satisfaction also has an impact on the academic success of the institution, student behaviors, student satisfaction and the power of the teacher to produce work, in short, organizational creativity (Çekmecelioğlu, 2005; Greenberg, 2002; Hutabarat, 2015; Jiang, 2005; Zhou and George, 2001). In this sense, the possibility of reflecting the negativity of the preschool teachers to the educational environments where young children are educated is an important issue to be taken into consideration. It has been observed that studies with preschool teachers on this subject are extremely limited. Thus, the aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between preschool teachers' organizational creativity (in terms of individual and administrative creativity) and job satisfaction. To achieve this purpose, whether preschool teachers' organizational creativity and job satisfaction make significant difference was also explored depending on their type of institution (public and private), longing for a career change, number of children in the class, professional seniority, and weekly working hours.

Methodology

The purpose of this research is to investigate the relationship between preschool teachers' organizational creativity and job satisfaction. Therefore, this research was conducted in accordance with correlational survey model. Survey model refers to “studies that determine the characteristics of the participants' views, interests, skills, abilities, attitudes, etc. about a subject or event” (Büyüköztürk, Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz & Demirel, 2008). In this study, after the organizational creativity and job satisfaction of preschool teachers were described, the correlation between these two variables was examined and comparisons were made in terms of various variables.

Participants

The participants of the study were comprised of 173 female preschool teachers who participate in the study voluntarily through “Google Form.” When the demographic distribution of participants was looked at, 71.1% of the participants work in public institutions and 28.9% of them work in private institutions. While 32.9% of the participants stated that they wanted to do another profession, 67.1% of them stated that they did not. 67% of the participants had less than 20 children in their class, 33% of them had more than 20 children in their class. 24.3% of the participants had 0-2 years, 22% of them had 3-5 years, 15% of them had 6-8 years and 28.7% of them had 9 years or more professional seniority. 61.8% of the participants worked 20-30 hours a week, 23.7% of them worked 31-40 hours a week and 14.5% of them worked 41 hours and more a week.

Data Collection Instrument

Personal Information Form. For the demographic data of the preschool teachers, Personal Information Form was used which included items about the type of institution (public or private), the longing for a career change, the number of children in the teaching class, the professional seniority of the teachers and weekly working hours.

Organizational Creativity Scale. Organizational Creativity Scale was developed by Balay (2010) and checked for its reliability and validity with pilot studies. It consisted of 3 dimensions with 38 items in total, of which 16 are individual items, 11 are administrative items and 11 are social items. While the item loadings in the factors of the scale ranged between .47 and .88, when the alpha values taken for each dimension were calculated, they equaled to .92 in the individual dimension, .93 in the administrative dimension and .95 in the social dimension. In addition, when the scale was combined and used in a single dimension, the total variance was 58%, which meant that the scale could be used for a single dimension. The items of the 5-point Likert scale could be marked as “totally disagree,” “slightly agree,” “moderately agree,” “strongly agree” and “totally agree.” When the arithmetic means of the scores obtained from the scale were checked, 1.00-1.80 was evaluated as “Very low,” 1.81-2.60 was evaluated as “Low”, 2.61-3.20 was evaluated as “Medium”, 3.21-4.20 was evaluated as “High” and 4.21-5.00 was evaluated as “Very high”. In this study, however, only individual, and administrative dimensions of the scale were used. The reliability values for this study for the Individual dimension of the Organizational Creativity Scale was .904 and the reliability value for the Administrative dimension was .928.

Job satisfaction scale. The Job Satisfaction Scale, developed by Hackman and Oldham (1975), was adapted to Turkish by Silah (2002). Taşdan (2008) conducted the validity and reliability measurement studies with school organizations and teachers. Therefore, this research adopted Taşdan’s (2008) Job Satisfaction Scale. The factor loading values of the scale were between .69 and .86. The total variance of the scale was 63.86%. Item total correlations ranged from .66 to .84. Cronbach’s Alpha value of the scale was found to be .95. The scale consisted of 14 items and was one-dimensional. The items of this scale, which was in the form of 5-point Likert scale, could be marked as “not at all satisfied,” “not very satisfied,” “somewhat satisfied”, “very satisfied” and “extremely satisfied.” In the evaluation of Job Satisfaction Scale, the ranges of job satisfaction scores were as follows: “14-24 points: Very low level”, “25-35 points: Low level”, “36–48 points: Medium level”, “49–59 points: High level” and “60–70 points: Very high level”. The reliability value of the Job Satisfaction Scale for this study was found to be .898.

Data Collection/Procedure

A form was created on “Google Form” by combining Personal Information Form, individual and administrative dimensions of Organizational Creativity Scale and the items of Job Satisfaction Scale. The person who did not fill in any question was blocked by the system from completing the form. Each form took approximately 5-10 minutes to complete. The link to the form created during the data collection process was delivered to preschool teachers via the Internet. A total of 173 female pre-school teachers completed the form and all of the forms were included in the study. It took approximately two months for the forms to be filled in by the teachers.

Data Analysis

In order to determine the appropriate analysis method to be used for the data obtained from the scales, the normality test was performed first. T-test, one-way analysis of variance and Pearson correlation analysis were used for independent samples, which are among the parametric tests for variables because of their normal distribution.

Findings

In this section, findings related to the purpose and objectives of the research are given.

Table 1: T-Test Results of the Teachers' Organizational Creativity in Individual and Administrative Dimensions and Job Satisfaction According to School Type

Scale	Institution	<i>n</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>S</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Individual Dimension of Organizational Creativity	Public	123	3.75	.511	171	2.003	.047
	Private	50	3.93	.594			
Administrative Dimension of Organizational Creativity	Public	123	2.75	.874	171	3.621	.000
	Private	50	3.32	1.053			
Job Satisfaction	Public	123	3.00	.753	171	3.546	.001
	Private	50	3.45	.762			

As shown in Table 1, there was a statistically significant difference depending on the type of institution between the preschool teachers' organizational creativity scores in the individual dimension ($t=2.003$, $p=.047<.05$) and organizational creativity scores in the administrative dimension ($t=3.621$, $p=.00<.01$), which was in favour of those working at private institutions. A statistically significant difference was found between job satisfaction scores of preschool teachers ($t=3.546$, $p=.001<.01$) in favor of teachers working at private institutions in terms of the type of institution.

Table 2: T-Test Results of Teachers' Organizational Creativity in Individual and Administrative Dimensions Scores and Their Job Satisfaction Scores in Terms of Longing for a Career Change

Scale	Longing for a Career Change	<i>n</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>S</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Individual Dimension of Organizational Creativity	Yes	57	3.79	.521	171	.219	.827
	No	116	3.81	.552			
Administrative Dimension of Organizational Creativity	Yes	57	2.63	.99	171	2.81	.005
	No	116	3.06	.91			
Job Satisfaction	Yes	57	2.63	.76	171	2.57	.011
	No	116	3.06	.77			

As seen in Table 2, there was no statistically significant difference between preschool teachers' organizational creativity scores in individual dimension ($t=.219$, $p=.82>.05$) depending on the status of longing for a career change, while organizational creativity scores in administrative dimension ($t=2.81$, $p=.005<.01$). This statistically significant difference was in favor of preschool teachers who did not want a different profession. A statistically significant difference was found between the job satisfaction scores of the preschool teachers ($t=2.57$, $p=.011<.05$) in favor of those who did not want to do a different profession according to the status of longing for a career change.

Table 3: T-Test Results of Teachers' Organizational Creativity in Individual and Administrative Dimensions Scores and Their Job Satisfaction Scores in Terms of the Number of Children in Classes

Scale	Number of students in class	<i>n</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>S</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Individual Dimension of	Less than 20	116	3.83	.54	171	1.00	.317
	20 and more	57	3.74	.53			

Organizational Creativity							
Administrative Dimension of Organizational Creativity	Less than 20	116	3.03	1.01	171	2.29	.023
	20 and more	57	2.68	.80			
Job Satisfaction	Less than 20	116	3.25	.75	171	3.04	.003
	20 and more	57	2.87	.77			

In Table 3, no significant difference was found between the pre-school teachers' organizational creativity scores in individual dimension ($t=1.00, p = .317 > .05$) with regard to the number of children in their classes. It was seen that there was a statistically significant difference between the preschool teachers' job satisfaction scores according to the number of children in their classes ($t=3.04, p=.003 < .01$) and the organizational creativity scores in administrative dimension ($t=2.29, p = .023 < .05$). These statistically significant differences were in favor of preschool teachers who have less than 20 students in their classrooms.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Analysis between Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Organizational Creativity Scores in Individual and Administrative Dimensions

Scale		Individual Dimension	Administrative Dimension	Job Satisfaction
Individual Dimension of Organizational Creativity	<i>r</i>	1	.271**	.176**
	<i>p</i>		.0	.021
	<i>n</i>	173	173	173
Administrative Dimension of Organizational Creativity	<i>r</i>	.271**	1	.621**
	<i>p</i>	0		.0
	<i>n</i>	173	173	173
Job Satisfaction	<i>r</i>	.176**	.621**	1
	<i>p</i>	.021	.0	
	<i>n</i>	173	173	173

** $p < .05$

As shown in Table 4, it was revealed that there was a low, positive, and significant correlation between pre-school teachers' individual and administrative organizational creativity scores ($r=.271, p < .01$). The results indicated a low, positive, and significant correlation between teachers' organizational creativity and job satisfaction ($r=.176, p < .05$). According to Table 5, a moderate, positive, and significant correlation between teachers' administrative organizational creativity and job satisfaction was also identified ($r=.621, p < .01$).

ANOVA results indicated that there was no statistically significant difference between preschool teachers' job satisfaction ($p=.097$), individual ($p=.473$) and administrative ($p=.056$) dimensions of organizational creativity scores in terms of professional seniority, and between their job satisfaction ($p=.357$), individual ($p = .270$) and administrative ($p=.715$) dimensions of organizational creativity scores concerning weekly working hours ($p > .05$).

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

The current research which was conducted to examine the relationship between the organizational creativity and job satisfaction of preschool teachers had 173 female preschool teachers as participants. In the analysis of data obtained from Personal Information Form, Organizational Creativity (Individual and Administrative Subscales) and Job Satisfaction Scale, t test for independent samples, one-way analysis of variance and Pearson correlation

analysis were used. While the organizational creativity and job satisfaction scores of the teachers were examined for each variable, it was calculated whether there was a statistically significant difference between the organizational creativity of the teachers in individual and administrative dimensions and the organizational creativity and job satisfaction.

As the organizational creativity scores of the preschool teachers increased in the individual dimension, the organizational creativity scores in the administrative dimension also increased. Accordingly, it can be claimed that the greater the individual creativity of the individual is, the more the organizational creativity of the administrative dimension is affected. Besides, it was recognized that the relationship between individual and organizational creativity was affected by different factors. For example, it was indicated that preschool teachers who were pleased to be preschool teachers had higher levels of organizational creativity in administrative dimension than those who were not satisfied with their profession. It may be surprising that preschool teachers thought that they had demonstrated their creativity in administrative sense although they believed that they did not reveal their creativity in individual sense. However, these teachers also have high job satisfaction as seen in another finding of this study and may have to use their creativity in organizational climate to deal with the administrative problems they face in order to practice their profession.

Preschool teachers working in private institutions had higher individual and administrative organizational creativity scores and job satisfaction scores than those working in state institutions. In the literature, there are studies showing that teachers working in private schools are higher than teachers working in public schools in terms of creativity (Fidan & Öztürk, 2015; Uğurlu & Ceylan, 2014) and job satisfaction (Perrie & Baker, 1997; Sönmezer, & Eryaman, 2008; Taşdan & Tiryaki, 2008). This situation suggests that teachers working in public institutions may have some internal institutional problems.

There was no statistically significant difference between the individual organizational creativity scores of preschool teachers depending on the number of children in their classes, professional seniority and weekly working hours. Looking at the creativity of preschool teachers from an individual perspective, the study by Zembat, İlçi Küsmüş and Yılmaz (2018) also showed that teachers' creative thinking tendencies did not change according to the number of children in their classrooms. A study by Nartgun and Demirer (2015) also found that the organizational creativity of administrators does not differ depending on professional seniority. When the job satisfaction scores of the teachers were examined, no statistically significant difference was found in terms of professional seniority variable. Some studies also have shown that preschool teachers' job satisfaction does not differ according to professional seniority (Şahin & Dursun, 2009; Eser, 2010).

It was found that there was a statistically significant difference between teachers' job satisfaction scores and administrative organizational creativity scores according to the number of children in their classes. The preschool teachers with less than 20 children in their class had higher job satisfaction scores than the teachers with more than 20 children in their class. Tekerci (2008) also notified that preschool teachers with fewer (10 and less) children had higher job satisfaction. Contrary to these findings, in some studies, there was no statistically significant difference between the job satisfaction scores of preschool teachers with regard to the number of children in their classrooms (Durualp & Kaytez, 2016; Perie & Baker, 1997). The results of the current study may be due to the fact that the number of teachers participating in the study is not similar or may suggest that teachers working with fewer children may have less work stress.

It was found that job satisfaction increased as teachers' individual and administrative organizational creativity scores increased. In the study of Yılmaz and Karahan (2010), it was revealed that organizational creativity had an effect on employee performance, while Çekmecelioğlu (2005) concluded that job satisfaction was affected to the extent that organizational climate supported employees' creativity. Greenberg (2002) also stated that the organizational creativity of the people who had job satisfaction while doing a job would be high. In a study conducted by Yılmaz and Izgar (2009) with teachers working in primary schools, it was expressed that there was a statistically significant relationship between teachers' organizational creativity and job satisfaction, and job satisfaction was significantly predicted by organizational creativity.

The current study assumed that the emotional bond established between the younger age group and the teachers affected some results (i.e., no change in job satisfaction in terms of professional seniority). This suggests that the level of children (such as primary school level and secondary school level) who teachers educate may have an impact on organizational creativity and job satisfaction. Therefore, it is recommended to carry out research investigating the organizational creativity and job satisfaction of teachers at different educational levels. This study, on the other hand, examined the relationship between organizational creativity and job satisfaction. However, there are other variables to which organizational creativity is correlated. Consequently, studies investigating the relationship between other factors (such as organizational support, administrative support, colleague support, resource adequacy, freedom, workload pressure, psychological climate in the environment) and organizational creativity can be conducted. The fact that the study group consisted of only women can also be seen as a limitation. Also, the number of teachers who participated in the study is less than expected which is an important factor for the generalization of the research results. For future studies, inclusion and comparison of other variables (gender, age, educational status, etc.) that affect teachers' organizational creativity and job satisfaction and conducting a study with a larger group of teachers are recommended. In addition, the reason why organizational creativity and job satisfaction scores of teachers working in state institutions were lower than teachers working in private institutions can be investigated.

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